

Data Specifications

Deliverable D2.1

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Authors	Christian Fotteler (INILAB)
Peer reviewed by	Kai Heussen, Lunodzo Mwinuka, William Ammentorp, David Tanase, Seyede Zahra Tajalli, Anton Troelsen, Anna Malkova, Henriette Dyhr Rahbek (Radius), Carsten Buhl Nielsen (Radius)
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Executive Summary

This deliverable defines data specification and data model for the 3PhaseInsight project, providing a shared technical and semantic understanding of the three-phase smart meter dataset delivered by Radius. It establishes standardised definitions for topology data (e.g., substations, transformers, feeders, and cables) and time-series measurements (e.g., voltage, active/reactive power, and harmonic distortion per phase), along with its naming conventions and relationships mappings across entities. The specification integrates multiple data sources, including raw CSV files, supplementary metadata, and additional contextual attributes, into a framework that supports accurate interpretation, data quality management, and alignment across project partners.

Building on this specification, the deliverable proposes a scalable hybrid data model that combines relational databases for structured grid topology and metadata with object storage for large-scale time-series data. The model introduces versioned topology graphs to capture grid network changes over time, thereby enabling traceability and reproducibility of analytical results, while metadata structures support data lineage, ingestion tracking, and storage of algorithm results. Measurements are stored in partitioned, columnar formats to ensure efficient querying at scale. These combinations lay a solid foundation for pipeline development, hence positioning the data model as a central enabler for the project's data infrastructure (D2.2 [1]) and subsequent solution pipeline.

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1 Introduction

1.1 About the project

The rapid electrification of the grid is placing more pressure on distribution networks, where increasing numbers of heat pumps, electric vehicles (EVs), and other power electronic devices introduce additional loads and often phase imbalance. At the same time, Danish distribution system operators (DSOs) generally lack detailed observability of low-voltage (LV) grids: topology records might have errors, phase-connection information is often dependent on the communication form of the meters and missing for some meters, and power quality monitoring is limited or absent at secondary substations. This lack of granular, per-phase visibility forces DSOs to rely on conservative planning assumptions, leading to unnecessary capacity buffers, delayed customer connections, and costly reinforcement measures that slow down the green transition.

Motivated by these challenges, the 3PhaseInsight project unlocks the value of per-phase smart-meter measurements by developing advanced analytics and scalable data-processing pipelines. The platform validates on a dataset of around 100,000 customers provided by Radius, a leading DSO in Denmark, demonstrating real-world performance at scale and establishing a proven foundation for broader deployment. The central idea is that modern smart meters can provide per-phase voltage, power, and harmonic information at a granularity that enables a new level of LV situational awareness. The platform delivers actionable insights through state-of-the-art data-driven and machine-learning algorithms, directly supporting more efficient operation, planning, and stakeholder-level data sharing.

The platform delivers a suite of modular Data Applications including per-phase topology correction, imbalance screening, harmonic analysis, and detection of significant electrification loads, such as heat pumps and EV chargers. These analytics are integrated into an open-source, cloud-deployable data-pipeline framework that supports scalable execution, modular workflow composition, and interoperability with DSO environments. By combining improved LV observability with replicable digital tools, the project aims to help DSOs target interventions more precisely, design new customer-facing services, and establish a pathway for broader sector adoption and future expansion of the analytics toolbox.

The goal of this deliverable is to provide a technical and semantic description of the data provided by Radius. It also provides a description of the developed data model, including data types and naming conventions, suitable for use in the 3PhaseInsight project. In this document, the terms Data Specification and Data Model can be used interchangeably.

1.2 Scope

This Deliverable covers the Data agreements and specifications that lay the foundation of the 3PhaseInsight project. The developed Data Model should be applicable to the entire delivered dataset that covers the radial grid. Since the delivery of the other datasets (island grid, mesh grid) was delayed, they are out of scope, and only some data apps have been tested with this data. While the presented model is specific to the use in the 3PhaseInsight context, other similar use cases aiming at building a scalable data pipeline for a low-voltage grid can also adopt it. The main goal of data specification is to provide a common understanding of the data being processed, which then helps with technical, architectural, and use-case-related discussions. The developed Data Model can be used to store Data in a relational database or translated to other databases as needed. For more information on the data model architecture, see D2.2 [1]

1.3 Approach

The basis for developing the data model is the raw CSV files containing time-series data and topology information. The relationships among the different entities (Smart Meters, Cabinets, Secondary Substations, and other components) were determined, leading to the development of a Data Model that combines file-based time-series data with structured data in a relational Data Model.

2 Reference Specifications

2.1 Consortium Agreement Data Specification

The data delivered by Radius follows a specification agreed upon by the project consortium. The defined specification is described in Table 1.

Table 1: Description of raw datasets specifications as received from Radius

Parameter	File (format)	Description
SECONDARY_SUBSTATION	Topology.csv	Serial number of the substation.
TRANSFORMER	Topology.csv	Serial number of the transformer.
TRANSFORMER_CAPACITY	Topology.csv	Transformer capacity in kVA, three-phase value.
LV_FEEDER	Topology.csv	Feeder number of the network under a certain transformer.
LV_FEEDER_FUSE_SIZE	Topology.csv	Ampere-per-phase capacity of the fuse connecting the transformer and the first bus of each feeder.
NODE1	Topology.csv	Bus 1 for the LV line, either at a distribution box (POD), or at the bus connecting the feeder to the transformer.
NODE2	Topology.csv	Bus 2 for the LV line, either at a distribution box (POD), or at the bus connecting the feeder to the transformer.
LV_CABLE	Topology.csv	Serial number of the LV cable.
CABLETYPE	Topology.csv	Code for cable core and insulation materials.
CABLE_LENGTH	Topology.csv	Length of the LV line in meters.
PHASESIZE	Topology.csv	Conductor size in mm ² , per phase.
PHASEMATERIAL	Topology.csv	Core material code (Aluminium/Copper).
CURRENT_CARRYING_CAPACITY_PIPE	Topology.csv	Ampacity per phase of the underground cable.
RESISTANCE	Topology.csv	Per-phase resistance in ohm/km.
REACTANCE	Topology.csv	Per-phase reactance in ohm/km.
METER_NUMBER	MeterAndCabinet.csv	Unique meter number linked to Timeseries.csv.
CABINET	MeterAndCabinet.csv	Cabinet (POD) number mapped to buses.
TIMESTAMP_DST	Timeseries.csv	Timestamp in GMT+DST (London time).
VOLTAGE_L1	Timeseries.csv	Voltage on phase L1.
VOLTAGE_L2	Timeseries.csv	Voltage on phase L2.
VOLTAGE_L3	Timeseries.csv	Voltage on phase L3.
ACTIVE_POWER_P14_L1	Timeseries.csv	Active power on phase 1 of the net-consumption meter.
ACTIVE_POWER_P14_L2	Timeseries.csv	Active power on phase 2 of the net-consumption meter.
ACTIVE_POWER_P14_L3	Timeseries.csv	Active power on phase 3 of the net-consumption meter.

Parameter	File (format)	Description
ACTIVE_POWER_P23_L1	Timeseries.csv	Active power on phase 1 of the net-production meter.
ACTIVE_POWER_P23_L2	Timeseries.csv	Active power on phase 2 of the net-production meter.
ACTIVE_POWER_P23_L3	Timeseries.csv	Active power on phase 3 of the net-production meter.
REACTIVE_POWER_Q12_L1	Timeseries.csv	Reactive power on phase 1 of the net-consumption meter.
REACTIVE_POWER_Q12_L2	Timeseries.csv	Reactive power on phase 2 of the net-consumption meter.
REACTIVE_POWER_Q12_L3	Timeseries.csv	Reactive power on phase 3 of the net-consumption meter.
REACTIVE_POWER_Q34_L1	Timeseries.csv	Reactive power on phase 1 of the net-production meter.
REACTIVE_POWER_Q34_L2	Timeseries.csv	Reactive power on phase 2 of the net-production meter.
REACTIVE_POWER_Q34_L3	Timeseries.csv	Reactive power on phase 3 of the net-production meter.
METER_NUMBER	Timeseries.csv	Meter number to be used with MeterAndCabinet.csv.

2.2 Data scale and batch delivery

The data was delivered by Radius over 3 batches:

- Batch 1: Data for 2,194 smart meters across 9 substations, without the additional data described below
- Batch 2: Data for 61,557 smart meters across 600 substations, including the 9 substations from Batch 1
- Batch 3: Data for 20,454 smart meters of meshed city grid. This was delivered later in the project, and has not been the main focus

2.3 Supplementary Information

Additional information to better describe and complement the shared dataset was also presented by Radius. This information is necessary to ensure data quality is maintained across several processing levels, shared platforms, and their processing lifecycle.

2.3.1 Topology

- To determine cable types from the CABLETYPE property, refer to cable catalogs
- The LV_FEEDER_FUSE_SIZE measurement is missing for a significant part of the data, this is a given constraint.
- NODE1 and NODE2 define an LV feeder or cabinet. The connection between two nodes is called a mainsection and can consist of multiple cables (subsections).
- Transformer configuration can be assumed to be Delta-Wye.

2.3.2 Timeseries

- Timestamps are GMT+1 with daylight saving time.

2.4 Additional Data

In addition to the datapoints mentioned in the Table 1, more datapoints were provided:

- Total Harmonic Distortion: THD_I , THD_U
- Information on whether a heatpump is connected to a meter
- Information on whether solar panels are connected to a meter and their capacity

3 Data Model

Due to the different nature of time-series data and relational data, such as topology data, the Data Model is designed to accommodate two complementary storage layers. The time-series data model is designed for *object storage* as columnar, partitioned files, while the structural and derived data is designed to be stored in a *relational database*, which provides referential integrity, joins across the grid hierarchy, transactional updates, and more complex query capabilities. The database is organised into two schemas. The schema names can be changed at will, but the default schemas are `lv`, which holds the grid topology, and `meta`, which holds metadata and analysis results. More infrastructural and architectural descriptions are presented in Deliverable 2.2 (Data Infrastructure) [1].

3.1 Topology Data

The topology data model covers assets and the topology graph. While the assets are captured as static objects, the topology graph is versioned and designed to capture topology changes over time, each change representing a newer version.

3.1.1 Assets

The `lv` schema first captures the physical assets of the LV network at both the grid and consumer levels, as shown in Figure 1. On the grid side, a `secondary_substation` contains one or more `transformers`, and each transformer supplies to one or more `feeders`. On the consumer side, a `cabinet` groups one or more `delivery_points`, and each delivery point is associated with one or more `meters`. Alongside their identifiers, the entities carry attributes relevant to the analyses: a transformer's rated capacity; a feeder's and a delivery point's fuse sizes; a substation's location; and per-meter flags indicating the presence of a heat pump or solar installation, along with the installed solar capacity.

Figure 1: Grid-topology assets in the 1v schema, representing the grid-side and consumer-side hierarchies.

3.1.2 Versioned Topology Graph

The physical connections of the grid components are modelled as a graph that sits alongside the assets as shown in Figure 2. To fulfil the requirement that physical connections change over time, the model stores the topology graph as versioned snapshots rather than mutating a single live copy. Each snapshot is identified by a `topology_version`; exactly one version is flagged as the current one, and each version records a processing level that distinguishes raw, cleaned, and cleaned-and-corrected reconstructions. Every row of the graph carries its `version`, so a snapshot can be read, compared, or retained independently of the others.

In a snapshot, a `node` represents one asset participating in the graph, which can be a feeder, a cabinet, or a delivery point, with a `node_type` attribute that identifies the kind of node. An `edge` represents a connection between two nodes. The physical conductors are modelled separately as `cables`, which carry the electrical properties used by the analyses, such as length, cross-section and material, current-carrying capacity, resistance and reactance. A single edge may correspond to an ordered run of several cables; this many-to-many relationship is resolved by the `edge_cable` table, whose sequence number preserves the ordering of cables along with an edge. Snapshotting the entire graph under a version has a second benefit beyond capturing topology versions: it gives every derived result a precise topology to refer to. As described in the next section 3.2, an analysis result can be pinned to the exact `topology_version` against which it was computed, so that results remain interpretable even after the topology is later revised.

Figure 2: The versioned topology graph in the 1v schema.

3.2 Metadata and Results

The `meta` schema stores metadata about measurements and workflow outputs. First, it enables tracking of ingested time-series files: the `file_index` table holds one row per file, recording its storage location and details such as the covered time interval and the row and byte counts. The `ingest_batch` table records ingestion runs that produced sets of files, retaining their source, status and summary statistics, so that every ingested file can be traced back to the batch that produced it. Second, the `meta` schema stores per-entity metadata and workflow results. The `meter` table records when a meter was first and last seen, how many rows it has contributed and structured summaries of its data quality, statistics and connectivity. The `run_result` table records the outputs of the data applications and algorithms in a single, uniform structure that lends itself well to being exposed via an API. It holds the source that produced a result, a confidence score, a typed label, and an optional structured result payload.

Figure 3: The meta schema holding the time-series catalog, lineage (file_index, ingest_batch), per-entity metadata and results (meter, run_result).

3.3 Time-Series Object Storage

The measurements are stored as columnar *files* organised within a partitioned directory structure. The files are partitioned by date and sharded by meter identifier (meter number). This allows a time-bounded or meter-specific query to read only the relevant directories instead of the entire dataset.

Each record corresponds to one meter at one timestamp and carries twenty-one measurements per reading across three phases: voltages, active power, reactive power and total harmonic distortion of both voltage and current (Figure 4). Files are first written to a staging area, and once a batch has been processed, it is promoted from staged to ready, where it becomes visible to consumers.

MEASUREMENT_RECORD		
timestamp	timestamp	natural key
int64	meter_number	natural key, = meter.id
double	voltage_l1	
double	voltage_l2	
double	voltage_l3	
double	active_power_p14_l1	
double	active_power_p14_l2	
double	active_power_p14_l3	
double	active_power_p23_l1	
double	active_power_p23_l2	
double	active_power_p23_l3	
double	reactive_power_q12_l1	
double	reactive_power_q12_l2	
double	reactive_power_q12_l3	
double	reactive_power_q34_l1	
double	reactive_power_q34_l2	
double	reactive_power_q34_l3	
double	thdu_l1	
double	thdu_l2	
double	thdu_l3	
double	thdi_l1	
double	thdi_l2	
double	thdi_l3	
string	dt	partition: date YYYY-MM-DD
int16	shard	partition: from meter id

Figure 4: Measurement records in object storage.

4 Conclusions

The goal of this deliverable was to create a specification for the time-series and topology files provided by Radius. The developed data model combines several technologies to ensure scalability and performance across different data types. This results in a clear, shared reference model that supports ingestion, querying, and analysis, and provides a common point of reference for discussions and future use cases. This document lays a foundation for the development of the data infrastructure (D2.2) [1] and the subsequent data pipeline in D4.1 [2], which presents pipeline application showcases and their source code and documentation.

5 References

- [1] 3PhaseInsight Consortium. Deliverable D2.2: Data infrastructure, June 2026. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21071943>.
- [2] 3PhaseInsight Consortium. Deliverable D4.1: Results of data pipeline applications showcase, June 2026. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21072541>.

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